

MANAGEMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING TO IMPROVE COMPETITIVENESS AND BUSINESS SKILLS OF NON-FORMAL EDUCATION'S PARTICIPANTS

WARMAN SURYAMAN

Sekolah Pascasarjana Universitas Islam, Nusantara. Email: warmansuryaman@uninus.ac.id

HENDI SUHENDRAYA MUCHTAR

Sekolah Pascasarjana Universitas Islam, Nusantara. Email: hendi@uninus.ac.id

WASKA WARTA

Sekolah Pascasarjana Universitas Islam, Nusantara. Email: waska.warta@uninus.ac.id

MUHAMMAD ANDRIANA GAFFAR

Sekolah Pascasarjana Universitas Islam, Nusantara. Email: andriana.gaffar@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

Low entrepreneurial skills and high unemployment rates are one of the many problems in the education sector, especially non-formal education as a supplier of human resources. This problem is caused by various factors, including PKBM graduates who have so far focused more on getting a diploma than getting skills and have the mindset that entrepreneurship requires large financial capital. Each PKBM has actually understood that in addition to obtaining a diploma, learning residents also need to be given certain skills based on entrepreneurship in order to achieve economic independence. However, in reality, PKBM is constrained in managing the implementation of entrepreneurship training. This study aims to determine (1) planning, (2) organizing, (3) implementation, (4) evaluation, (5) supporting factors, (6) inhibiting factors, and (7) to find solutions and improvement efforts made by PKBM on the management of entrepreneurship training programs. The research is based on management theory and empowerment theory using a qualitative case study type descriptive approach. Data collection techniques using interviews, observation and documentation studies. The results of this study indicate that the management of entrepreneurship training carried out in three PKBMs in West Java is: (1) Planning is carried out with a needs analysis, (2) Organizing determines a curriculum that fits the needs, syllabus, and lesson plans as well as a clear division of tasks for each HR, (3) Implementation focuses on optimizing entrepreneurship-based life skills training, (4) Evaluation is carried out by incidental or scheduled monitoring by all parties involved, (5) Several supporting factors include the presence of partners and budgetary assistance from the government and the community, (6) Inhibiting factors are in the form of technical constraints such as access to product marketing, limited tools and materials for learning residents, PKBM infrastructure facilities, etc., and (7) Solutions to obstacles that occur, namely improving communication, optimizing infrastructure and human resources, and facilitating complaints from the learning community. Recommendations from this study, it is hoped that PKBM heads will further optimize the entrepreneurship training program where tutors always improve their competence, so that residents are able to apply and read marketing opportunities for products resulting from the training.

Keywords: Management, Training, Entrepreneurship, PKBM.

INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian nation is currently entering the 21st century, a period full of challenges and competition that requires high-quality human resources (HR). Human resources are a determining factor in nation building, in addition to natural resources, be it biological, non-biological and man-made, as well as scientific and technological resources. The prolonged monetary crisis has become a difficult hurdle to deal with, in fact it is increasingly emphasizing the need for the development of strong human resources, knowledgeable and superior as well as skilled but still based on religious values, culture and local context (Ifnaldi, 2021: 171).

Center for Community Learning Activities (PKBM) which teaches the science of production and distribution. Learn business science to produce as many goods/services as possible and learn trade science to seek business profits and require capital in the form of money which is not small. The entrepreneurial program is not solely like that, the essence is PKBM which builds an entrepreneurial atmosphere so that learning residents like challenges, are creative, innovative, and have the courage to take or manage risks (character). Learning citizens really need positive stimulation to develop entrepreneurial principles that are needed in the future (Gunartin, Soffiatun, & Hayati, 2018: 37). However, in reality, the entrepreneurship skills training held at PKBM has not been managed well because various obstacles are still found. Since elementary education, students have not been taught creativity and independence. So they have not had the opportunity to express their imagination through various simple to complex activities, and they also need to learn to direct and manage themselves so that they can support themselves. Starting from there, students will think about providing benefits by supporting other people and are able to think that they can also have an impact on other people and the environment. Education in human life is directed at changing behavior where this change concerns aspects of human knowledge and attitudes because education will determine the quality of existing human resources. As is known, education is pursued through three educational pathways, namely formal education, non-formal education and informal education.

The current assumption is that an entrepreneur is born because of hereditary factors, only descendants of entrepreneurs can be successful in the business sector. While this is impossible for ordinary people, apart from that, there are also those who think that talent is the factor that determines success in business. Those who do not have talent will continue to experience losses and eventually go bankrupt. Likewise, if someone has talent in business, their business will quickly achieve success. In fact, there are also those who think that an entrepreneur's success is due to his luck (Sibarani et al, 2019: 24).

People who have not been able to build an economic foundation certainly want economic independence so that they can prosper their families through entrepreneurship. This is hampered by limited capital to create a business to support his family. Capital in running an entrepreneur is not only in the form of money, but can be in the form of physical and non-physical capital. Physical capital can be in the form of money, buildings, cars, assets

and so on. Meanwhile, non-physical capital includes expertise, communication skills, creativity, and so on. Independence is an attitude that every person should have.

Independent means self-regulating power, self-directed action, not dependent on the will of others, the thing to follow one's own will. The measure of the progress and independence of a nation cannot only be in the form of per capita income, or the size of the debt, but is more fundamentally related to its people. So, in the midst of the needs of people who are developing their economy independently, entrepreneurship training in PKBM is expected to provide support in the form of providing non-physical capital that can create economic independence for the community so that it becomes an intelligent society and a prosperous society. Likewise, with the objective conditions at the study sites, namely PKBM Bina Mandiri Cimahi City, PKBM Mekarsari West Bandung Regency, and PKBM An-Nur Ibun Bandung Regency.

Entrepreneurial spirit and entrepreneurship education is an option as well as one of the expected alternative solutions where by implementing entrepreneurship education in non-formal education, especially in the three PKBMs in West Java, the learning residents will get sufficient knowledge about entrepreneurship. Armed with this knowledge, after they graduate, they can use it to run a business independently so they no longer need to be busy applying for jobs here and there by handing out diplomas and not necessarily being accepted (Aini, 2014: 4).

Based on several of these problems, it is necessary to make an effort from PKBM so that the goals of organizing entrepreneurship programs for graduates of Community Learning Activity Centers can be achieved, in line with current needs, especially in changing the mindset of students learning to become independent through entrepreneurship.

In connection with this, researchers can determine and focus their research related to problems in PKBM with the title "Entrepreneurship Training Management to Increase Competitiveness and Business Skills of Non-formal Education Students".

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

1. Management

Management is organizing and the ability to move people to work and behave in accordance with the leader's expectations so that the expected goals can be achieved quickly, precisely and economically. These objectives include; man, money, methods, materials, machines, and markets that need to be planned, organized, directed, evaluated, so that the desired results are achieved. Furthermore, James A. F. Stoner and Charles Wankel in Siswanto (2021: 16), provides management limitations as follows: 'Management is the process of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling the efforts of organization members and of using all other organizational resources to achieve stated organizational goals'. This statement implies that management is the process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the efforts of organizational members and the use of all other organizational resources to achieve organizational goals.

2. Training

The training in this research is an effort to make students in PKBM through skills learning so that they are independent for entrepreneurship. This is in line with what was stated Hatu (2010: 243) that:

Training is a process for the community to become empowered, encouraging or motivating individuals to have the ability or power to determine their life choices and training must be aimed at groups or layers of society that are left behind.

While according Wallenstein (1992) in Cross (2020: 28), training is:

'Empowerment is a social action process that primate's participation of people, organizations, and communities toward the goals of increase individual and community control, political efficiency, improved quality of community live and social justice'.

The above understanding, that training is a process of social action that increases the participation of people, organizations and society towards the goal of increasing individual and community control, politics, improving people's lives and social justice, where individuals and groups get access to power to control resources and control over his life.

The purpose of this training is as part of empowerment so that students besides having academic knowledge and attitudes, are also independent entrepreneurs. Thus the students are empowered, both literacy and economically and superior. This is in line with the training objectives, as stated by Iskandar (2017: 54):

The occurrence of empowerment causes four aspects (cognitive, affective, connotative, and psychomotor) to be able to contribute to the creation of the aspired community self-reliance, in society there will be sufficient insight, equipped with adequate skill skills, strengthened by a sense of need for development and conscious behavior of these needs.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach that is oriented towards a 'qualitative descriptive design'. The aim of this type of research is to carry out a systematic, factual and accurate description of the facts and characteristics of the population of a particular area. Therefore, this research does not need to look for or explain interrelationships, test, hypothesize, make predictions or obtain meaning and implications, but what is needed is to conclude and explain the data then analyze and interpret it. In this study, researchers tried to perceive and interpret the actions carried out by the managers of PKBM Bina Mandiri Cimahi City, PKBM Mekarsari Kab. West Bandung and PKBM An-Nur Ibun Kab. Bandung.

The method applied in this research is a case study which aims to obtain an overview of all aspects of certain social phenomena that are relevant to the research to be achieved, so by choosing this method a clear picture is obtained so that in the end the research objectives can be achieved, namely regarding the symptoms. symptoms that occur at the

moment and stimulate in the future. This is in accordance with the objectives to be achieved, namely disclosing data clearly regarding the management of community training through non-formal education in partnerships at PKBM Bina Mandiri Cimahi City, PKBM Mekarsari District. West Bandung and PKBM An-Nur Ibun Kab. Bandung, to increase entrepreneurial independence.

Research locations were carried out in three PKBMs, namely: PKBM Bina Mandiri Cimahi City, PKBM Mekarsari West Bandung Regency, and PKBM An Nur Ibun Bandung Regency, West Java.

The research subjects or main sources for obtaining research data are the Head of PKBM, Teachers (Tutors), Field Coordinators, and Students (learners).

The data required in this research includes primary data, namely data obtained directly from interviews with respondents and secondary data, namely data that has been collected and processed by other parties but is taken as a reference in the research.

DISCUSSION

According to the research findings, it shows that entrepreneurship training at Three PKBM in West Java is appropriately carried out by determining needs, in the context of planning the entrepreneurship training program in the author's view, it is in accordance with established procedures and takes into account various potential experiences of learning residents which are expected to help students learn in creating economic independence from the results of training and determining the business field that will be pursued. This is as confirmed by Reza, Rukanda, & Kartika (2022: 97) that:

Life skills education provides opportunities to face future life challenges in the real world. In addition to getting knowledge about the skills of learning residents, they also get business opportunities and build a very broad business that can help the family's economy to be better and besides that it can also reduce the unemployment rate.

Based on the research findings, it appears that the organization of the entrepreneurship training program has gone well. This can be seen from several activities in the organization carried out such as the division of tasks for tutors and employees according to their respective competencies, the creation of an organizational structure that provides an overview of tasks, authority, responsibility and coordination. One example is the assignment of a person in charge or a skills program coordinator who is responsible for everything related to the skills program at PKBM. In addition, the coordinator also assists tutors in preparing and developing training materials that will be used so that they can be used by residents learning during the training process. This is also done so that tutors are able to respond to all forms of requests due to changing times and there is an increase in the competence of tutors in adapting to the times. From there it can be seen that there is a division of tasks according to the competence or expertise of each to always improve the competence of each HR, this is in line with Manda's opinion (2016: 90) that:

By dividing tasks, it is hoped that each member of the organization can improve their specific skills (specialization) in handling the assigned tasks. If the organization is carried out haphazardly, not in accordance with one's area of expertise, then it is not impossible that it could lead to failure in the implementation of work.

The organization and division of tasks cannot be separated from the role of the Head of PKBM as Manager, as Kurnianingsih believes (2018: 15) that:

"The role of the school principal as a manager in improving teacher competence is shown by the existence of program preparation, school organizational structure and clear division of tasks, mobilizing staff, teachers and employees".

In addition to being able to increase competence, a clear division of tasks according to competence can also provide a sense of comfort, especially for tutors so that it can provide an increase in motivation and concentration in carrying out tasks.

In accordance with the interpretation in the study, it shows that the implementation of the entrepreneurship training program focuses on training centered on learning citizens and is conditioned by individual and small group training that is adapted to the characteristics of learning residents. The environment around PKBM, which is mostly an industry with tutors who come from practitioners, also helps learning residents get an idea of what they can do if they have mastered certain life skills obtained from the results of training at PKBM. In the author's view, this is appropriate because in the training process students should be made more active and creative. This is as stated by Malaikosa (2021: 305) that:

"The success of developing life skills depends greatly on the extent to which students see and emulate the characteristics given by teachers, parents and community members. Teachers can help students to acquire life skills by implementing learning activities that are suitable for developing, building and training students' characteristics."

The role of the tutor has changed from those who previously mastered conventional learning techniques, now it has undergone changes with the entrepreneurship training program. In the view of the author, this has brought a new paradigm in which entrepreneurship training programs take into account the learning experiences and needs of today's learning citizens. This is in accordance with Sari's opinion (2016: 17) stated that: "Training programs must contain activities and learning experiences that can meet previously determined training objectives"

Based on the interpretation in the research, it shows that the evaluation of entrepreneurship training programs is based on evaluations carried out by internal and external parties. The evaluation results are documented and reviewed by the central curriculum development team to evaluate the success of the entrepreneurship training program at PKBM. This is very appropriate for PKBM to do so that the success of the entrepreneurship training program can be communicated to students and the community so that it can easily support decision and policy makers.

In the author's view, program evaluation is aimed at measuring the context of programs regarding rational objectives, program background, and needs that arise in planning. Likewise, process evaluation is aimed at looking at the implementation process, starting from the smoothness of the process, conformity with the plan, supporting factors to obstacle factors that arise in the implementation process and the like. This is in accordance with Suci's opinion (2021: 21) that: "Evaluation aimed at seeing the implementation process, both regarding the smoothness of the process, conformity with the plan, supporting factors and inhibiting factors that arise in the implementation process, and the like."

The administration of the results of the evaluation carried out by the PKBM head was also carried out quite well by the three PKBMs in West Java. This is where all the evaluation results documents that have been carried out have been well documented by the PKBM and MSME partners. With administration, it will be easier to control and evaluate what has been done.

In addition, this stage is oriented towards alignment and balancing efforts as data and information have been obtained from the evaluation results. This evaluation can make a basis or reference for various things or aspects that should immediately become a priority for improvement and improvement in the future. In other words, the documentation of the evaluation results can be used as a reference for improvement as well as control for the quality of implementing entrepreneurship training in the future. Interpretation results state that PKBM facilitates the dissemination of evaluation results of entrepreneurship training programs and for follow-up both at the PKBM level and at the national level to then provide recommendations and input for entrepreneurship training programs in the future. Dissemination of evaluation results according to the author is the right thing.

Based on the interpretation of the research, it shows that the implementation of the entrepreneurship training program in the three PKBMs in West Java is supported by the person in charge of the program. According to the author, this factor will create tutor human resources who have abilities in accordance with their expertise, complete and adequate facilities and infrastructure, there is a team of training tutors headed by the team responsible for the skills program. Apart from that, there is online media as a tool to help in the training process and product marketing, there is CSR assistance from the company in providing supporting facilities for the smooth running of training activities, there is socialization and provision of support from universities to students studying.

Apart from assistance from other parties, PKBM has its own business entity and collaborates with the Education Department through PP PAUD-DIKMAS, the community, MSME partners, and alumni. This is in line with management theory in general, as expressed by Terry and Rue (2021: 92) which confirms that: "effective or not a management implementation is also influenced by whether there is responsibility in the team". This also confirms that a team is needed to make the entrepreneurship training program in the three PKBMs in West Java more accelerated and run more optimally. Apart from that, having adequate training infrastructure and competent human resources in entrepreneurship training at PKBM is a very fundamental element. Collaboration with

the Office of Education and the community, especially learning residents, provides its own support in the smooth implementation of the program.

Management functions which are sequential, gradual, continuous, sequential and mutually reinforcing activities and constitute a complete and continuous unit have been applied by the three PKBMs in West Java. The management of the PKBM program is determined by the involvement of stakeholders who work together to achieve the specified goals in order to achieve standards for implementing PKBM activities. Direktorat Pembinaan Pendidikan Masyarakat (2010) defines "a standard is a minimum criterion that is determined to be a benchmark for the implementation of activities". The definition of standard is in line with Komaruddin's opinion (1994) that "a standard is a determined measure of quality or value as an example for comparison, a norm, or a good quality criterion".

Based on this, it is known that the management of the program implemented is determined by the managerial ability of the program manager who is innovative, creative and comprehensive, which will determine the quality of the program the institution manages. To improve program management, there is collaboration between PKBM managers, program administrators (program administrators), program tutors, so it is hoped that the PKBM program can be accredited. However, in reality, in the field, various inhibiting factors are still found even though the management's managerial abilities have met the standards.

The three PKBMs in West Java have attempted to minimize and overcome various obstacles by formulating and trying various solutions. The first is to improve program planning. Second, by optimizing the distribution of tasks and trying to add tutors who are competent in their fields. Third, the PKBM administrators made rescheduling for students who were unable to attend. Fourth, learning residents who have limited tools and materials are given the opportunity to use the equipment provided by PKBM to open their own businesses. Fifth, providing soft skill and hard skill training for human resources and learning residents so that they have an interest in processing and marketing their own products. Finally, the PKBM administrators also consulted with the local PP PAUD-DIKMAS to determine standard evaluation formats and training programs.

Entrepreneurship training management not only equips learning citizens with life skills to produce a product but also how the skills gained from training can provide opportunities to open businesses independently. Because entrepreneurship education is able to equip students with various entrepreneurial competencies which will later bring great benefits in their lives. Entrepreneurship education is also a formulation for the nation's problems, namely unemployment, poverty, weak public health and others. Various ways are used by tutors and participants to market their training products, including by utilizing online media, participating in various fashion exhibitions and competitions, as well as collaborating with other agencies that require uniform manufacturing services. Apart from that, PKBM has collaborated with various businesses, both MSMEs and companies, as internship sites for participants.

Training teaching materials that are made in accordance with the curriculum make this training more focused. This entrepreneurship training is not only limited to how participants can sell the products they have made. But it is also accompanied by economic knowledge in order to increase their productivity. This was done because according to Lopus, Amidjono, and Grimes (2019: 1): "Given that the economic education literature links financial literacy to improved worker productivity, decreased absenteeism, and entrepreneurial success".

CONCLUSION

The entrepreneurship training program to improve the competitiveness and business skills of PKBM non-formal education participants was implemented according to management principles and was generally successful. Established partnerships with various industries and intensive efforts to market products resulting from life skills training, also support this success.

- a. Planning for the entrepreneurship training program at PKBM is carried out consistently with the stages of identifying needs, identifying organizational capabilities, setting goals, preparing the program and planning socialization.
- b. Organizing the training program is carried out according to planned needs, including preparing the syllabus and lesson plans according to the implemented curriculum and arranging the PKBM organizational resources.
- c. The implementation of the program is centered and adapted to the characteristics of the learning community, trainers or tutors from practitioners help the learning community get an idea of what they can do if they have obtained the results of training at PKBM.
- d. The evaluation process is carried out by providing evaluation formats for the achievement of results, processes and the impact of program implementation on improving the training outcomes of learning residents.
- e. Supporting factors for the training program include the availability of human resources who have the skills and expertise, good relationships between PKBM managers and companies that are active in implementing CSR programs and also the Education Department through PP PAUD-DIKMAS, the community, MSME partners, and alumni.
- f. Factors inhibiting entrepreneurship training programs include limited time availability for both students and MSME partners, the planning process is often less than mature due to incidental programs, a lack of tutors who have special competencies, and a lack of soft skills and hard skills training provided so that marketing of training products is still less than optimal. . The evaluation format and training program do not yet have standards, which is also an inhibiting factor which results in the evaluation process not fully running well.
- g. The solutions developed in this entrepreneurship training program include improving planning, optimizing the division of tasks in a strict and proportional manner, adding

tutors who are competent in their fields, increasing the intensity of soft skills and hard skills training for human resources and students so they have an interest in processing and marketing their own products, and so on. improve the communication capacity of learning citizens. PKBM also continues to strive to add and optimize infrastructure facilities.

References

- 1) Aini, Q. (2018). *Implementasi Pendidikan Kewirausahaan untuk menumbuhkan minat wirausaha siswa Kelas X pada program Entrepreneur di SMA Excellent Alyasini Pasuruan* (Skripsi, Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim).
- 2) Cross, R., Foster, S., O'Neil, I., Rowlands, S., Warwick-Booth, L., & Woodall, J. (2020). *Health promotion: global principles and practice*. London: CABI.
- 3) Ifnaldi, I. (2021). Pendidikan Kecakapan Hidup. *DAR EL-ILMI: Jurnal Studi Keagamaan, Pendidikan dan Humaniora*, 8(2), 170-188.
- 4) Iskandar, D. (2017). Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Dalam Bidang Pertanian Oleh Lembaga Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Di Desa Jadimulya Kecamatan Langkaplancar Kabupaten Pangandaran. *Moderat: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 3(1), 49-61.
- 5) Gunartin, G., Soffiatun, S., & Hayati, H. F. A. (2018). Pusat Kegiatan Belajar Masyarakat Sebagai Tempat Alternatif Menumbuhkan Kemandirian Wirausaha Warga Belajar”(Studi Pada PKBM Insan Karya Pamulang Tangerang Selatan). *Pekobis: Jurnal Pendidikan, Ekonomi, dan Bisnis*, 3(2), 30-48.
- 6) Hatu, R. (2010). Pemberdayaan dan pendampingan sosial dalam masyarakat (suatu kajian teoritis). *Jurnal inovasi*, 7(04).
- 7) Komaruddin. (1994). *Ensiklopedia Manajemen, Edisi ke-2*. Jakarta: Bina Aksara.
- 8) Kurnianingsih, E. (2018). Peran Kepala Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Kompetensi Guru. *Indonesian Journal of Education Management & Administration Review*, 1(1), 11-18.
- 9) Lopus, J. S., Amidjono, D. S., & Grimes, P. W. (2019). Improving financial literacy of the poor and vulnerable in Indonesia: An empirical analysis. *International Review of Economics Education*, 32, 100168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iree.2019.100168>
- 10) Malaikosa, Y. M. L. (2021). Penguatan life skills peserta didik dengan pendekatan ekonomi kreatif. *Idaarah: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan*, 5(2), 300-312.
- 11) Manda, M. (2016). Fungsi Pengorganisasian dan Evaluasi Peserta Didik. *Kelola: Journal of Islamic Education Management*, 1(1), 89-101.
- 12) Reza, R. M., Rukanda, N., & Kartika, P. (2022). Upaya Pendidikan Life Skill Dalam Menumbuhkan Kewirausahaan Warga Belajar Paket C. *Comm-Edu (Community Education Journal)*, 5(3), 92-97.
- 13) Sari, L. R. (2016). *Pelaksanaan Pelatihan Kecakapan Hidup (Life Skills) di Lembaga Pembinaan Khusus Anak Klas I Kutoarjo*. (Skripsi, Universitas Negeri Semarang).
- 14) Sibarani, C. G. G. T., Armayanti, N., Irwansyah, I., & Suharianto, J. (2019). *Dasar-Dasar Kewirausahaan*. Medan: Yayasan Kita Menulis.
- 15) Siswanto, B. (2021). *Pengantar manajemen*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- 16) Suci, Rahmanda. (2021). *Evaluasi Pembelajaran Daring Era Pandemi Covid-19 Pada Kelas II A di SDN 3 Negara Ratunatar Lampung Selatan*. (Skripsi, Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung).
- 17) Terry, G. R., & Rue, L. W. (2021). *Dasar-Dasar Manajemen Edisi Revisi*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.